

Active Research: Document

Collect & Create

List Data Types, Formats, and Size

Understand the data you are working with and the implications for data security, data storage, and data sharing. This information should be captured in your project README File, lab notebook, and/or DMS Plan.

- **Types:** List the data you will collect or create, e.g., tabular data, survey data, experimental measurements, models, software, audiovisual data, physical samples, etc.
- **Formats:** Note what format(s) your data will be in, e.g., plain text (.txt), comma-separated values (.csv), geo-referenced TIFF (.tif, .tiff). Using open formats ensures the long-term usability of data and are recommended for sharing and archiving. If you need to convert or migrate your data files, be aware of potential data loss or corruption and take appropriate steps to avoid or minimize it.
- **Amount/Size:** Estimate how much data will be produced throughout the project and if the production rate will change. This helps determine data storage requirements both during and after the project.

Outline Data Collection Methods

Explain how data will be collected and/or describe any existing data being used (including outlining any Data Use Agreement terms). Determine how you will document data collection methods. This information should be captured in your project README File, with links to the appropriate locations.

- **Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN):** Allow users to enter protocols, observations, notes, and other data using a computer or mobile device. Find [ELN guidance across the Longwood Medical Area](#).
- **Lab Protocols:** Describe reusable methodologies in all fields of study. Consider using a publishing platform to collaboratively write and publish interactive and dynamic protocols.
- **Inventory:** Track data files, physical samples, and/or materials using a simple spreadsheet, database, or collaborative tool. Some ELNs have a built-in inventory tracking system.
- **Data Management Tools:** There are many other places to capture information for specific aspects of project management (e.g., OSF, GitHub), or specific data workflows (e.g., DataJoint, OMERO, REDCap).

★ [protocols.io](#) is a collaborative platform for publishing step-by-step methodologies

The Countway Library offers protocols.io Premium for the HMS/HSDM/HSPH research community. Premium accounts expand access to private and secure workspaces, increased storage capacity, and dedicated support.

Utilize Metadata Standards

Metadata is structured information that describes, explains, locates, or otherwise makes it easier to retrieve, use, or manage research data. Whenever possible, it is best to consult community standards. Metadata can be tracked in lab notebooks, lab databases, and/or data repositories.

- **[Metadata Schemas](#)**: Labeling, tagging, or coding system used for recording cataloging information or structuring descriptive records (e.g., MIBBI, ISA-Tab, Darwin Core).
- **[Controlled Vocabularies](#)**: Predefined terms by a community or research group (e.g., CMS coding).
- **[Ontologies](#)**: Variety of controlled vocabulary that defines components and describes relationships among components (e.g., MeSH, MGED, Gene Ontology).
- **[Technical Standards](#)**: Established norm or requirement for a repeatable technical task establishing uniform criteria, methods, processes, and practices (e.g. ISO-8601 date and time format YYYYMMDD)

Create Data Documentation

Good documentation allows you to understand, use, and share your data and helps other researchers discover, access, use, repurpose, and cite your data. In addition to lab notebooks, documentation can be maintained in a variety of forms and will be utilized when depositing data in a repository:

- **[README](#)**: Text file located in a project-related folder that describes the contents and structure of the folder and/or a dataset so that a researcher can locate the information they need.
- **[Data Dictionary](#)**: Defines and describes the elements of a dataset so that it can be understood and used later (also known as a codebook).

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[Analyze & Collaborate](#)

Facilitate Data Analysis

Analysis-ready datasets have been responsibly collected and reviewed so that analysis of the data yields clear, consistent, and error-free results to the greatest extent possible. Since raw data are often unstructured, data cleaning is part of the analysis process. Always keep a read-only copy of original raw data, and then document further processing and analysis.

- **[Tidy Data Principles](#)**: Each variable is in its own column, each observation in its own row, and each value in its own cell. This format facilitates data visualization and analysis using software languages.

Maintain Code Documentation

Establish documentation for code, scripts, and software. Version control is used to track changes to your files so you can collaborate with team members or go back and retrieve specific versions of your files later.

- ★ **Utilize [GitHub](#) to store, track, and collaborate on software projects**

GitHub is a web-based service for Git repositories (i.e., groups of tracked files). GitHub is good for code development; however, it is not a robust platform for sharing. Consider capturing an instance of your GitHub Repository in an established repository, e.g. Zenodo or Harvard Dataverse, to facilitate long-term preservation.

Document Data Analysis Protocols

Interpretation or analysis of data requires proper documentation. The type of analysis you perform depends on the type of data you're using and what the goal of your research project is. There are several strategies to enhance your analysis and fully capture your process:

- **Jupyter Notebook** is an interactive computing environment to create documents that include code, plots, text, images, and more. This streamlines analysis and provides a platform to rerun your work.
- **High-Performance Computing (HPC)** helps make your analysis more efficient and faster. HPC environments are connected to storage clusters where you can store the data being processed.
 - **[HMS Research Computing](#)** offers the O2 cluster, bioinformatics consultative services, and other assistance to support needs, analysis methods, documentation, and data transfer.
 - **[FAS Research Computing](#)** offers the Cannon Cluster, FASSE Cluster, consultative services, and other assistance to support needs, analysis methods, documentation, and data transfer.

- ★ [HMS Research Core Facilities](#) *provide specialized services, equipment, and staff for data analysis support*
HMS Research Core Facilities provide access to highly specialized services, equipment, and staff and can provide advice on documenting data analysis relating to the technology in their specific Core.

Document Image Management and Processing

Documenting the manipulation and analysis of images can help with processing and provide greater transparency of techniques. Additionally, sharing images in open formats (when possible) supports long-term access.

- **Recommended Open Formats:**
 - **Still images:** TIFF, JPEG 2000, PDF, PNG, GIF, BMP
 - **Moving images:** MOV, MPEG, AVI, MXF
- **[Image Management Resources:](#)**
 - **[OMERO](#):** Software for management, visualization, and analysis of microscope images
 - **Adobe Bridge:** Free software for locally organizing images
 - **ImageJ:** Free open-source, Java-based image processing and display tool
 - **Tropy:** Free, open-source software to organize and describe photographs of research materials